

Hello, dear professor

I apologize for taking up your time.

I wrote an article about a new hypothesis that reveals the fundamental principles of natural selection. What is selected by natural selection? Why is it chosen? In this paper I argue that I have found the principles that are selected by natural selection.

The important thing is that this article is a preprint. Maybe there is a problem with the translation. Maybe the wording and arrangement of the content is not correct. I want you to pay attention to the general topic of the article, the new hypothesis.

I am waiting for your feedback. Please send me your comments, suggestions and criticisms.

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The new hypothesis is not about selection at the molecular level. In this article, I will not discuss structural selection, selection based on the components of molecules and cells, selection based on biochemical laws and physics and chemistry, and other selections. In this article, I would like to discuss another type of selection at the population, individual, allele, and cell levels.

tip; There may be other principles that are selected by natural selection. But in this article, I will examine the fundamental principles of the new hypothesis, namely, providing energy and nutrients and providing security.

Point 2; I have other articles to publish that present new psychological hypotheses based on the fundamental principles of the new hypothesis. In other articles, I have discussed the reason for the evolution of music, the evolution of human societies, the evolution of cultures and values, the evolution of inventions, sociological theory, economic theories, the cause of human pain and suffering, the cause of happiness and satisfaction, the cause of the behavior of creatures, the compatibility of populations, I explain the evolution of populations based on the fundamental principles of the new hypothesis.

Is it possible that the new hypothesis provides a new understanding and interpretation of evolution and biology?

Dear readers, if you find new and useful concepts in this article, please send the article link to science enthusiasts, scientists, professors and students.

The new hypothesis of the fundamental principles of natural selection/ What is chosen? What characteristics are selected?

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Abstract

The current view of biologists about evolution and adaptation is that; The characteristics of alleles are selected by natural selection based on survival and reproduction. This is true, but it is only a general definition and it ignores important points and leads to a misunderstanding of adaptation, survival, natural selection and evolution. Because this attitude limits selection by natural selection at the level of survival and reproduction. This fact does not reflect evolution well. But I found another level of selection, choice and screening. Before selection based on survival and reproduction, there is another level of selection which are principles that help survival and transfer of genes to the next generation. In this article, I interpreted and analyzed the neck of the giraffe, the beak of Darwin's Galapagos birds and many other cases of natural selection and biology based on a new hypothesis, better and more acceptable than the current evolutionary point of view. In this article, I argue that the selection is based on the fundamental principles of the new hypothesis. That is, selection and choice of useful or harmful features of alleles, selection of deletion or preservation of genes and alleles by natural selection, selection of adaptation and evolution of populations is not based on survival and reproduction. Rather, the selection is done by natural selection based on the fundamental principles of the new hypothesis. The explanations and interpretations of this new hypothesis are much closer to reality.

Keywords: selection principles; survival principles; new hypothesis; compatibility principles; alleles characteristics

Introduction

Natural selection selects genes that increase the survival of the organism and reproductive success or the success of transferring genes to the next generation. A gene that causes characteristics that help survival and transfer genes to the next generation, that characteristic is useful for the organism. **1 (Richard Dawkins 1976)** According to Darwin, a (successful) organism is an organism that survives and continues to reproduce. **2 (Ernest Mayer 2002)** Alleles that have characteristics that lead to the survival and reproduction of organisms are selected and maintained by natural selection. **3 (Campbell Biological 2011)**. Natural selection is a process that, over successive generations, leads to the creation of hereditary traits that increase the probability of survival and reproduction of organisms in a population. In other words, natural selection is a process in which individuals adapted to the environment have a greater chance of survival and reproduction and can pass on their genes to the next generation. In contrast, individuals that are not compatible with the environment are removed from the species and cannot pass on their genes. During this process, genes adapted to the environment remain in the species. **4(T. Ryan Gregory 2009)**

As you saw above, biologists believe that traits are selected by natural selection based on the success of organisms in survival and reproduction. But are the selection of hereditary characteristics limited by natural selection only at the level of survival and reproduction? Aren't there other characteristics on which natural selection can select?

What are the characteristics of these genes adapted to the environment? Beneficial gene has no other definition except based on survival and reproduction? More importantly, what is the issue of choice? What is selected? Are alleles and phenotypic traits selected only on the basis of survival and reproduction?

Example: Every organism, whether it is an animal or a plant, fights for its survival. If it is an animal that is killed by predators, it must fight the predators. If it is a hunter, it must fight with other hunters for hunting. **5 (Darwin 1859, new German edition of The Origin of Species 2002, quoted by Ernst Mayr 2002)**

In my opinion, hunters, hunt for provide energy and nutrients. The prey competes with the hunters in the struggle for survival to provide itself security. In fact, the struggle for survival is the struggle for provide energy and nutrients by hunters. But the struggle is a prey to provide one's own security. Here, predators compete with other predators for provide their energy and nutrients. For example, cheetahs hunt gazelles for provide their energy and nutrients. But the gazelles must run faster than the cheetah for their survival or in fact to provide their security so as not to be hunted. The cheetah also tries to run faster than the gazelle in order to hunt her, and provide their energy and nutrients. Cheetahs compete with each other for provide their energy and nutrients. Cheetahs may compete with wolves and lion's for provide their energy and nutrients.

I accept that the characteristics, behavior and body parts of organisms are ultimately measured and selected by natural selection based on survival and reproduction (passing on one's genes to the next generation). But in my opinion, this description is general and reductionist. Because it limits the useful features of genes only at the level of helping survival and reproduction. As I argue in this article, selection based on survival and reproduction does not reflect the reality of evolution well.

I will give an example so that you can better understand that the useful feature of genes should not be limited only at the level of survival and reproduction. *True, in the end it is survival and reproduction that are measured. But details and factors that help survival and reproduction should also be considered.* For example; Apollo spacecraft took man to the moon. All the structures and components of Apollo were built for the purpose of traveling to the moon. If we say that all these components and equipment of Apollo were made for the purpose of "traveling to the moon", this is also true and correct. But if we go into the details of the spacecraft structures, we will see that each of the internal and external structures of the Apollo spacecraft were designed and built for a specific purpose. For example, the chair was made only for its occupants to sit. The fuel tank is built to supply fuel to the spacecraft. The oxygen capsule is for passengers to breathe, And... Therefore, each of the internal and external structures of Apollo is designed for a specific purpose, whose ultimate goal is to help the spacecraft reach the moon. If the spacecraft does not succeed in going to the moon, we say that the goal of going to the moon has failed. But when we get into the details of the reasons why the spacecraft did not go to the moon, there are many possibilities. For example, maybe the failure of one or several important parts, or the failure of its components, not enough fuel, not reaching the necessary acceleration to leave the Earth's atmosphere, which may be due to the weakness of the components and poor fuel. Or there may be many other reasons.

It is true that the goal of the spacecraft is to reach the moon. However, the components of the spacecraft should each have their own special functional purpose. For example, if there is a problem with the spacecraft's fueling system, then the trip to the moon will not be possible, but this is a problem in the spacecraft's fueling and energy supply system. Sometimes, in order to reach the truth, the task and function of the components of the spacecraft must be evaluated not according to the general task, but sometimes according to the specialized and specific task. These goals must all be achieved together to make the trip to the moon a success. Some of these goals are so important and necessary that if one of these goals is not achieved, the trip to the moon will not be achieved. In other words, the main components of the spacecraft are each selected and choice to reach the moon.

With this example, I wanted to explain that although the ultimate goal of organisms is survival and reproduction, there are factors that help survival and reproduction. Currently, biologists do not exactly determine what these characteristics that help survival and production are? I found a new hypothesis that shows that, before evaluating and selecting the characteristics of alleles and genes based on survival and reproduction, there is another level of evaluation and selection that are fundamental principles that contribute to survival and reproduction. In other words, the evaluation, measurement and selection of useful and harmful features of alleles is based on specific principles that the new hypothesis explains.

Now I present a new hypothesis that reveals that selection is not based on survival. Selection is not only based on the transfer of genes to the next generation. Survival is not selected by natural selection as you define it. *In fact, natural selection performs choice, screening and selection based on the fundamental principles of the new hypothesis.* Reproduction is one of these basic principles.

The fundamental principles of the new hypothesis (characteristics that are selected by natural selection.)

- 1- I predict that selection is most likely done by natural selection based on the fundamental principles of energy and nutrient supply.
- 2- One of the selections by natural selection is selection based on the fundamental principles of providing security.
- 3- Another selection probably occurs based on the fundamental principles of adaptation to environmental conditions such as temperature and humidity, etc.

4- Another hypothesis that I propose, but I will not discuss it much in this article, is the selection based on the fundamental principles of success in reproduction or success in transferring genes to the next generation.

If allelic characteristics in organisms can fulfill the fundamental principles of the new hypothesis, or act according to these principles, these alleles lead to adaptation and ultimately lead to survival and reproduction.

Example; Selection based on the fundamental principles of providing energy and nutrients

"Although the life of every plant depends on water. But the plant that grows on the edge of the desert is engaged in a special fight against water shortage. 6(Darwin's Origin of Species, German edition, 2002; quoted in What Is Evolution? Ernst Mayr, 2002) Water is essential for providing energy and nutrients to organisms and plants. 7(Campbell Biology 2011) Interpretation;The plant on the edge of the desert is struggling to supply its energy and nutrients, which is water.

A plant that is more resistant to water shortage than other members of that population is more likely to survive. 8(Ernst Mayer 2002) Interpretation based on the principles of the new hypothesis, a plant that is superior in supplying its energy and nutrients to other members of the population and is more resistant, has a higher chance of survival. The plant can survive by storing energy and nutrients. By sending its roots deep into the earth, it supplies its energy and nutrients. Here selection is done by natural selection based on the basic principles of energy and nutrient supply.

Darwin says; Since the individuals of the population reproduce more than they survive, then there is a battle for survival among the individuals of the population. 9(Darwin 1859)

interpretation; In fact, the battle for survival is the same as the battle for 1- providing energy and nutrients for yourself and your children, 2- fighting for the security of yourself and your children.

To understand evolution and natural selection, we must know the details of the characteristics that help survival and reproduction.

Materials and methods (Research methods and data interpretation)

This article is written theoretically without empirical research and mathematical data. I collected the data of this article through the method of library research and documents and based on the new hypothesis I found, I will present a new interpretation. I use other people's empirical data to analyze this new hypothesis, only our interpretation is different. I hope that in the future I will be able to arrange new experimental tests and mathematical analysis to argue this new hypothesis. I will invite others to do the same.

(Suppose I am a biologist conducting experimental research and experiments. I imagined that I had discovered these books and articles that I read from other biologists through observation, experimental research and study. Without compromising the nature of the important content of biology. That is, I observed their observations in the same way as them, I also observed them in detail, only our interpretations were different. This idea is just a way to better understand this new hypothesis. I am not going to dream and philosophize. I could not create a new hypothesis from scratch. I had to find a strong theory by which to explain these principles of the new hypothesis. Mr. Darwin's theory of evolution and natural selection helped me. Almost all biologists agree with Darwin's theory of evolution. I also accept Mr. Darwin's theory of evolution.)

Just to better understand this hypothesis, I pretended to be Mr. Darwin and found birds with different beaks in the Galapagos Islands. Now, what interpretation, answer, theory or hypothesis can I offer about how the beaks of these birds came about? Of course, to explain his findings, Darwin later read Malthus's article on population, which deals with this important issue; Although the population increases by reproduction by geometric exponential, but because food increases by mathematical

exponential, the population cannot increase explosively. Factors such as: 1-food shortage 2-competitors and enemies 3-dying and not reaching reproductive age 4-destructive and harmful environmental factors such as floods and earthquakes prevent the geometric growth of the population. 10 (Darwin 1859)

Based on these four factors, Darwin proposed natural selection to explain evolution. The text inside the parenthesis is the fundamental principles of the new hypothesis that I found. 1- lack of food (lack of energy and nutrients supply) 2. Competitors and enemies (competition with enemies is actually competition for energy and food supply and competition for self-protection or is to provide security) 3. Dying and not reaching reproductive age (not reaching reproductive age and not passing genes to the next generation) 4. Destructive and harmful environmental factors such as floods and earthquakes, etc. (lack of compatibility with environmental conditions such as temperature and humidity, etc.)

In fact, 1- Not providing energy and nutrients 2- Not providing security 3- Not adapting to environmental conditions such as temperature, humidity, pressure, etc., random and destructive events and factors such as floods and earthquakes, etc. 4- Lack of reproduction Either not reaching reproductive age or not transferring genes to the next generation. These are the factors that prevent the population from growing exponentially. I show in the article that choice and screening and selection by natural selection are done based on these fundamental principles. I based my hypothesis on these four fundamental principles and purposes. These are the fundamental principles of natural selection or the fundamental principles biological that most characteristics, evolutionary traits and behaviors can be better explained based on these principles. Remember these principles well. These principles are important to understand this hypothesis.

You can even assume that (I am Mr. Malthus) Mr. Darwin uses the new hypothesis that I found (instead of Malthusian theory) and interprets the beaks of Galapagos Island birds, evolution, natural selection and biodiversity are based on the fundamental principles of the new hypothesis.

Perhaps this misunderstanding arises in the new theory that natural selection has an ultimate goal that can predetermine the shape and progress of the evolutionary goal. This opinion has no place in the new theory and is wrong. These fundamental biological principles and goals have remained unknown until now. This has caused us to not understand the purpose and process of evolution as it should be.

Some of the questions that the new hypothesis seeks new answers to.

Should parents care for their children, provide food and protect them from enemies, be described only as survival or success in passing on genes to the next generation? Isn't there a better classification to separate food preparation and child protection? Protecting children and providing food are two very important but completely separate things.

Should the function of body parts and desirable behavior or traits of organisms be described as a whole in the name of survival and reproduction? Based on what characteristics does natural selection increase the frequency of genes in intragroup competition in a population?

Different species compete for survival. Based on what criterion and purpose does natural selection preserve or eliminate species? What are the characteristics of a good gene and a bad gene in terms of natural selection? Why did fish fins become legs of amphibians, reptiles, mammals and wings of birds?

For what purpose do the different organs of living organisms work and evolved? What was the purpose of the evolution of the different beaks of Darwin's Galapagos birds? What is the main purpose of living things to move? What do beneficial genetic mutations mean? And what useful features should it have?

The fundamental principles of the new hypothesis

These principles can be called the fundamental principles of natural selection, the fundamental principles of the new hypothesis, or the fundamental principles of biology.

With a philosophical argument, I want to say that without observing and implementing these principles by all organisms, their survival and reproduction will be impossible.

Note: In this article is "provide" means; supply, meet, earn, realized, obtained, get, fulfilled.

1- Selection and choice by natural selection based on success in reproduction and transfer of genes to the next generation

Didn't the first organisms (replicator or RNA) or all other organisms including bacteria, plants and animals, insects all need to multiply and reproduce or transfer their genes to the next generation to continue their generation? Reproduction can be considered as one of the fundamental purposes and principles of natural selection. Because without the transfer of genes to the next generation or reproduction, living organisms cannot continue to reproduce, and there will be no children and generations, and species will become extinct. Some by sexual reproduction and some by asexual reproduction, mammalian reproduction, reproduction by egg laying, body parts related to reproduction, all these were subject to natural selection. Success in reproduction and transfer of genes to the next generation in all organisms is their main purpose and it is considered by natural selection for selection and screening and chosen.

2- Selection and choice by natural selection based on provide energy and nutrients

Don't primitive organisms need energy and nutrients (organic materials) to reproduce and have children? Providing energy and nutrients means all the substances that an organism needs to survive and perform its biological activities. Like water and oxygen, carbohydrates, proteins, lipids, iron, calcium, vitamins, sunlight for plants, almost the energy and nutrients of all organisms are provided by plants. Most organisms need nutrients to make organic macromolecules. There is a need for energy supply to make organic macromolecules. In short, they need energy and nutrients.

All known organisms need carbon to produce organic molecules such as protein and nucleic acids and carbohydrates. The success of the formation and existence of life depends on the covalent bond between carbon and nitrogen and oxygen and hydrogen and the production of sugar from carbon by plants. Carbon life can make different molecules that are necessary for the evolution of different organisms, from the biological needs necessary for survival. Organic macromolecules such as protein, carbohydrates and nucleic acids, lipids require nutrients and energy to be made. **11 (Campbell Biology 2011)** What is selected, screened and chosen; There are features that provide nutrients and energy. I mean by providing energy and nutrients; Different processes of catabolism for energy production (energy supply) and anabolism process, which is any required material (nutrients) for the construction of cell components (cytoskeleton, mitochondria, ribosome and other components of the cell, components of proteins and genes). Providing and obtaining all the materials and energy needed by the cell is done by the characteristics and behaviors, cellular components and body parts. These characteristics are selected by natural selection based on the principles of providing energy and nutrients. Example; The giraffe's neck is selected by natural selection based on the fundamental principles supply of energy and nutrients. (Figure 1a) *In short, all organisms need energy and*

nutrients. Any traits that help provide energy and nutrients are selected for by natural selection.

3- Selection and choice by natural selection based on provide security. Didn't primitive creatures need security for survival and reproduction?

It has become increasingly clear that life-history patterns among the vertebrates have been shaped by the plethora and variety of immunological risks associated with parasitic faunas in their environments. Immunological competence could very well be the most important determinant of life-time reproductive success and fitness for many species. It is generally assumed by evolutionary ecologists that providing immunological defences to minimise such risks to the host is costly in terms of necessitating trade-offs with other nutrient-demanding processes such as growth, reproduction, and thermoregulation. ¹²(Robert L Lochmiller, Charlotte Deerenberg 2003)

Higher durability or safety than others can increase their reproduction. This feature or principle is favored or selected in the evolution of all organisms by natural selection. The need to provide security can have other names. The need for protection and safety. some traits and characteristics of organisms are used to provide security. For example, the immune system of organisms, the skin of organisms, defensive enzymes, white blood cells, deer and cow horns, elephant tusks, bee and snake stings, fighting and defensive skills of animals and more...

Providing security means all the actions, traits, behaviors and characteristics and body parts that are done to protect and defend all the constituent parts of the body. Providing security against the invasion of enemies, diseases and germs and viruses, protection against conflicts with sexual rivals, protection against environmental factors such as harmful rays of sunlight. Providing security for this reason is one of the fundamental principles of natural selection, because it is chosen and selected and screened by natural selection in successful adaptation and in successful survival and reproduction.

Some of you may say this is not security. It is protection or immunization, or fighting against external factors. Or you want to choose another name and function for it. Maybe you don't agree with the term provide security. But I show that selection by natural selection has evolved for protection, for safety and security, for security adaptations, for survival adaptations in all organisms. Features such as immune system and defense behaviors and ... are present in the body of vertebrates and most organisms. I named this practice provide security.

Note: The need to survive is different from the need to provide security in organisms. The need to survive or the need for survival is a broader concept and for the survival of organisms, there is a need to provide energy and security and adapt to environmental conditions and reproduction. This is the survival instinct. Survival instinct means the efforts of organisms to provide energy and security, reproduce and adapt to environmental conditions.

Interpretation of sexual choice based on the fundamental principles of

the new hypothesis; Sexual selection is the selection of characteristics from specific genes and alleles by a female or sometimes by a male. For example, when a female peacock chooses a male peacock, it selects him based on the fundamental principles of the new hypothesis. 1-By looking at the feathers of the male peacock, the female knows that this male peacock has been well fed. In other words, in the provide of energy and nutrients has been successful. 2-Also, it has survived with this beautiful tail, which means it has managed to secure itself. Sexual selection sometimes indicates health in the supply of energy and nutrients and a healthy metabolism in general. The different colors of birds and butterflies are due to success in providing good energy and nutrients and a healthy metabolism to provide energy and nutrients, which has been done by sexual selection. Sexual selection is actually an assessment based on providing energy and nutrients and providing security.

An example of selection based on the fundamental principles of provide security, provide energy and nutrients, Sexual selection or transfer of genes to the next generation

New data and tests of the origin of the elongated neck of the giraffe *Giraffa camelopardalis* have provided fresh insight into the origin of this trait. All attempt to test one of two main hypotheses – that of natural selection via advantages from feeding on trees above competitors (Darwin, 1871) or intra-sexual (male–male) competition via advantages found in clubbing rivals more effectively in competition for females (Simmons & Scheepers, 1996). Both mechanisms should result in longer necks and both are demonstrably advantageous to their bearers (Pratt & Anderson, 1982, 1985; Cameron & du Toit, 2007).
 Quoted from 13 (Rob E Simmons, Res Altwegg 2010)

(I define a successful gene and allele based on the new hypothesis as follows. Genes and alleles are considered to be successful and useful to create characteristics, behaviors and organs of the body in order to 1-provide energy and nutrients, 2-provide security, 3-adapt to environmental conditions such as temperature and humidity, etc., and 4-reproduce. As a result it helps the survival of organisms. It is a genes and an alleles that has good characteristics and does useful work.)

For example, In the same environment, there may be giraffes with different neck lengths. If something causes the loss of low shrubs, giraffes with shorter necks do not get enough food, energy and nutrients. They do not survive to reproduce. But if some giraffes have long necks and can use from the leaves of tall trees for provide energy and nutrients, they will survive and reproduce. After a few generations, the surviving giraffes will have longer necks because they can provide their own energy and nutrients to survive. if a gene leads to long legs for an animal, long legs can be considered an evolutionary advantage in the environment if they help provide energy and nutrients, provide security for that animal. example: 1- With its long legs and long neck, the giraffe can reach the leaves on top of the trees and provide its energy and nutrients from the leaves. (Figure 1a)

In fact, the selection of long legs and tall neck of the giraffe by natural selection was due to success in providing its own energy and nutrients.

This long-necked giraffe succeeds in providing its own energy and nutrients, it will most likely be successful in production, so it will pass the long-necked trait and allele and gene to its children.

2- Giraffes can also provide yourself security (protect themselves) by kicking predators like lions with their long legs. Kicking to the hunters violently will drive them away from the giraffe and help security the giraffe. (Figure 1b) The long legs make the giraffe's body somewhat out of the reach of predators. Even a long neck can strike predators with a whipping motion and drive predators away from the giraffe. This leads to the provide security of the giraffe. In this way, a giraffe with long legs will survive longer and probably be more successful in reproduction. But long legs are only a special case that leads to the fulfillment of fundamental biologic needs and not a general case. Because long legs may be useful for the giraffe, but the same long legs annoy the mouse and are not suitable.

The reason why the long legs and long neck of the giraffe was selected by natural selection was due to the success in providing energy and nutrients, and providing security (Sexual selection that helps transfer and copy certain genes to the next generation). A female giraffe probably chooses long necks and legs because they are successful in providing energy and nutrients and providing security.

The first evidence to confirm natural selection was selective coloration.

During his research in 1849 to 1860, Henry Walter Bates saw butterflies that were not naturally poisonous in the virgin forests of Brazil. But in terms of patterns, they imitated poisonous species. As soon as a pattern of new colors and patterns was found in the poisonous butterfly, the non-poisonous butterfly imitated it. In 1864, Fritz Muller discovered that poisonous species mimic each other's colors. Thus, the insectivorous birds eating one type of these poisonous butterflies was enough to avoid eating others that were similar and the same color as this type. In this way, several types imitated each other, much less were killed by enemies. (Ernest Mayer 2002)

Interpretation; Poisonous butterfly moths use poison to repel attackers from themselves so they don't get killed. Or their cheek poison keeps them safe from predators. Thus, if an insectivorous bird eats a poisonous butterfly, and becomes ill, it will never eat that butterfly again. A non-toxic butterfly can provide its security by imitating the color of poisonous butterflies. Natural selection favors butterflies that can take care of themselves or provide itself security. This choice and selection is based on the fundamental principles of provide security. The non-poisonous butterfly protects itself by imitating the shape and color of the poisonous butterfly (provide itself security).

4- Selection based on compatibility with environmental conditions such as temperature, humidity, attraction and gravity, atmospheric pressure, light and wind, etc.

Didn't all organisms need to adapt to environmental conditions? (such as adaptation in hot or cold environmental conditions, adaptation of some in water and some on land, etc.) To survive, organisms needed other useful properties such as adaptation to environmental conditions. Organisms could not survive without adapting to environmental conditions. Different organisms, the characteristics required for adaptation in hot or cold environments, plants in rocky or clay soil, living in high or low light, adaptation of atmospheric pressure on land and in water, adaptation to hot or cold water environment,

on land or in water, salt water or fresh water, the need to adapt to the pressure of deep sea water, the need for homeostasis or maintaining the internal balance of the body based on environmental conditions, and many other things that I call the need to adapt to environmental conditions. Fish in the sea and another fish in a fresh water river, penguins in the pole, adaptation of frogs in water and land, plants in deserts and some in snow and rainy environment and some environment full of moisture. Organisms evolved based on the atmospheric pressure on Earth or in the sea and the Earth's gravity. (Perhaps if there was life on other planets, the creatures of the planet would evolve based on the atmospheric pressure and gravity of that planet.)

Note: In this article, I argue about 1- selection based on provide energy and nutrients and 2- selection based on provide security. In my opinion, these two principles have the greatest influence, tendency and orientation in evolution and adaptation, through selection and screening by natural selection. Maybe there are other fundamental principles that are involved in chosen and screening and selection; Like selection at the molecular level and other things that I don't know at the moment.

New interpretation of genetic drift, gene flow and natural selection based on the fundamental principles of the new hypothesis/ What is chosen? Why is it chosen?

Biologists consider the forces that change the frequency of alleles, adaptation and evolution of the population to be mutation, genetic drift, gene flow and natural selection. Changes in allelic frequencies that cause evolution and adaptation are considered traits that help survival and reproduction. A gene can become useful under the influence of a certain environment and a certain phenotype. But the same gene, allele and phenotype may be harmful in another environment. [14\(Campbell Biology 2011\)](#) But genetic drift, gene flow, natural selection and genetic mutations must have characteristics so that natural selection can select on it, and change the population. Some mutations create useful traits that can change and evolve a population. But how is it possible that genetic drift and gene flow can change the population without considering allele characteristics? More importantly, what are these useful features and characteristics? The important issue is that so far no attention has been paid to an important issue and that is; Alleles have properties that were previously unknown in biology and evolution. In fact, the characteristic of alleles that natural selection affects their frequency as a factor; These fundamental principles are 1-providing energy and nutrients, 2-providing security, 3-adapting to environmental conditions such as temperature, humidity, pressure, light, wind, etc. 4-Reproduction or success in transferring genes to the next generation, the reason for the change in the frequency of alleles is these factors and the basic principles of the new hypothesis.

The new hypothesis says; Traits are not selected solely on the basis of survival and reproduction and are not defined on the basis of survival and reproduction. I hope I have expressed my meaning correctly. I mean, it's true that ultimately all traits, alleles, genes, adaptations, and evolution of populations are measured by survival and reproduction. But the features exist according to the fundamental principles of the new hypothesis that help survival and reproduction. The change in the frequency of alleles in the population is selected by natural selection according to these characteristics of the fundamental principles of the new hypothesis. In other words, before the selection of alleles and genes of a population based on survival and reproduction, There is a another level of selection, screening and choice.

We must have a correct attitude towards genetic drift and gene flow. Genetic drift randomly removes some characteristics of the alleles of a population based on the fundamental principles of the new hypothesis or causes the abundance of alleles with other characteristics based on the fundamental principles of the new hypothesis. But the gene flow moves the characteristics of the alleles, which are the same characteristics based on the fundamental principles of the new hypothesis, among the populations.

An example of selecting and choice alleles by natural selection based on the principles of providing energy and nutrients (there is competition between competing organisms for providing energy and nutrients.)

The Russian ecologist (G.F.Gause) cultivated two protist species, *Paramecium Aurelia* and *Paramecium Caudatum*, under constant conditions. He provided them with a fixed amount of food every day. When Gause cultivated the two species separately, the population of each species grew rapidly and remained stable within the tolerance capacity of the culture medium. When Gause cultured both species together, *Paramecium caudatum* was destroyed in the culture medium. Gause argued that *Paramecium Aurelia* was nimble in obtaining food. He concluded that two species competing for a common resource cannot coexist forever in the same place. 15(Campbell Biology Book)

Interpretation; In my opinion, this example shows competition for provide energy and nutrients. In the competition for energy and nutrients, natural selection selects and preserves those that succeed in acquiring and providing energy and nutrients. Natural selection maintains and supports *Paramecium Aurelia* that is more adept and capable of providing its own energy and nutrients. It is a selection based on success in providing energy and nutrients by natural selection. Adaptability should be defined as the ability to supply energy from various plant and animal sources, water and oxygen, etc. In fact, a slight superiority in energy supply (acquiring energy and nutrients, finding energy and nutrients, digesting, breaking down, transferring and moving energy and nutrients) can lead to the elimination of a weaker competitor. (In this article and based on the fundamental principles of the new hypothesis, weak means; Weak and unable to provide energy and nutrients. Or in provide energy and nutrient is poor) Organisms that have characteristics in their alleles and phenotype that make them successful in providing energy and nutrients will be successful in survival and reproduction. Not having the right phenotype and allele to provide energy and nutrients, or in other words, failure to provide energy and nutrients is equal to the death of the organism.

An example of the selection and choice of alleles by natural selection based on the fundamental principles of provide security

Drosophila melanogaster has an allele that makes it resistant to several types of insecticides, including DDT. The frequency of this allele in the laboratory strain of *Drosophila melanogaster* in the early 1930s (before the use of DDT) was zero percent. But in the strains that originated from the wild types collected in 1960 (with more than 30), the frequency of this allele reached 37%. One hypothesis says that the aforementioned alleles arose as a result of mutation between 1930 and 1960. Another hypothesis says; It is possible that this allele was present in the population in 1930, but it was very rare. In both cases, the increase in the frequency of the DDT resistance allele has occurred because the insecticide DDT, as a very strong poison, has created a strong natural selection force in the *Drosophila* population. Individuals from the population that did not develop resistance to DDT would die out. Few people who have the allele resistant to the poison reproduce and pass on the property of resistance to the poison to the next generation. The frequency of the allele that causes resistance to the poison will increase in the population that has been exposed to the poison. 16(Campbell Biology 2011)

New interpretation based on the fundamental principles of the new hypothesis: these changes are not random. Rather, natural selection by preferring the alleles that maintain and provide the safety (security) of the individuals in the population, causes survival and adaptive evolution. Natural selection will eliminate individuals from the population who cannot protect (provide security) themselves against DDT. But those who have the allele to provide security against the insecticide, evolution leads to their adaptation to their living environment. In this example, the selection via natural selection was based on the principles of provide security, And adaptive evolution has definitely occurred for the intention and cause and purpose of securing the safety (provide security) of *Drosophila*. Natural selection preserves any allele that helps secure (provide security) organisms.

For example, the ;(Example from Campbell's Biology book) Researchers in the study of the parus major bird in Veland Island found that the survival and reproduction rates of two populations of these birds are different.

Females of these birds in the east of this island have more survival and reproduction than the central population. The reason for that is the better adaptation of the birds of the east of the island to the environmental conditions. Although gene flow occurs between the two populations and reduces the genetic diversity of the island, researchers ask why the eastern population is more successful in adapting than the central population despite the gene flow. They attribute this to the genetic flow of the central population by populations of birds from Europe that breed with these birds. European birds are less adapted to this island. The gene flow has caused the central population to enjoy less adaptation in this island. 17(Campbell Biology 2011)

But the problem is not only gene flowing. The gene flow is good at explaining gene mix and intermixing. But gene flow is flawed in explaining natural selection. In general, in the whole science of biology, the characteristics of useful genes and alleles are only referred to as reproductive power, survival and reproduction. Based on the results I obtained, this case has more details that have been ignored until now. The useful features of genes and alleles should be sought in providing energy and nutrients and ensuring their security.

The traits are based on energy supply and security, which determine which alleles can be more effective in adaptation.

For example, in the population of the central part, it is less adaptable, most likely, if it is investigated, the investigation indicates that this bird is due to the lack of energy or food, or lack of security, or less adaptation to environmental conditions such as temperature and humidity, etc. The reason for less compatibility is the presence of alleles that make them unable to provide their energy and security or adapt to environmental conditions such as temperature and humidity and etc.

It is likely that if the eastern population, which is better adapted, is field-tested, the eastern population could provide its energy and security better than the central population.

Gene flow should consider the characteristics of genes. These characteristics of phenotypes (supplying energy and nutrients and providing security and adapting to environmental conditions such as temperature and precipitation, etc.) are chosen and select subject to natural selection. When organisms enter a new environment, if they can get food and water from the new environment, or the energy and nutrients they need, provide their security against predators and competitors, as well as with the cold environment. or also, adapt to the cold or hot environment, humidity and atmospheric pressure, etc., it can be said that the population of these organisms found a compromise with the environment. Genes generally develop in a population in which the environment and the population can provide energy,

nutrients, and security against enemies and competitors, and adapt better than competitors to environmental conditions such as temperature, humidity, pressure, etc.

If we examine a population that has been transformed by immigration, the transformations must be neutral or deleterious changes that have no effect on the survival of the population. If they are useful, they must have undergone a transformation in obtaining the amount and type of energy and nutrients from different sources, or in the transformation and decomposition of energy and nutrients (the process of body metabolism and cellular metabolism), or in their behavior and characteristics. Also, these beneficial changes should help provide security of the people of that population and the security of this population should be provided better than other populations. Or if the environment changes, such as a storm or flood, or the arrival of predators, parasites, viruses, etc., their security should be strong. Compared to those who did not undergo gene flow, the population in which the gene flow place due to migration will be better able to provide for their security. Also, if these changes are harmful, as in the above example, which weakened the survival and reproduction of birds in the central population, the reason for these harmful changes should be sought in the characteristics of the alleles that the immigrants brought with them. The alleles that are harmful were introduced into the central resident population, and probably the population has weakened in one or all of these cases of providing energy and nutrients, providing security, adapting to environmental conditions such as temperature and humidity, etc., and reproducing. Genetic drift and gene flow are not sufficient to explain evolution and adaptation. Gene flow and genetic drift must consider the characteristics of genes. Genetic drift and gene flow can evolve and adapt in a population when they change the characteristics of the population in providing energy and nutrients, and providing security.

Genetic drift and gene flow do not directly produce traits by themselves. Gene flow transmits and spreads beneficial or harmful traits in providing energy and nutrients, providing security, adapting to environmental conditions such as temperature and humidity, and reproductive traits among populations. Genetic drift removes allelic characteristics of a population based on energy and nutrient supply, security, adaptation to environmental conditions such as temperature and humidity, etc., and reproductive characteristics, by earthquakes or floods, etc., this causes or It is possible that other characteristics of other alleles become abundant in the population. Genetic drift and gene flow are not direct factors on survival and reproduction. When one population enters another population, when do changes in allele frequency, adaptation, and evolution occur in the population? When in alleles, the new feature of providing energy and nutrients, providing security, adapting to environmental conditions such as temperature, humidity, pressure, light, wind, etc. and changing the characteristics of reproduction occurs in the population.

An example of selection and choice by natural selection based on fundamental principles of the provide security

I would like to argue here that provide security is one of the fundamental principles of natural selection that is choose and selected. In Indonesia, a carrier crab carries a sea urchin on its back. This is for his own protection. When the attacking fish attacks it, the crab pulls the sea urchin towards the fish, thus the fish gives up hunting the crab. Sometimes crabs use jellyfish to secure themselves. **18(Campbell Biology 2011)** Why has this behavior evolved in this type of crab? When an attacking fish attacks a crab, the crab pulls the sea urchin towards the fish, thus provide its own security. In fact, this work has evolved with the aim of providing security. Natural selection chooses the behavior that leads to success in securing the security of organisms and maintains and accepts it. In some organisms, behaviors have evolved to ensure their safety (provide security) by carrying other organisms. Success in securing the security of organisms is an important factor in the success in survival and reproduction of organisms. The important point is that security is an important evolutionary trait that is subject to natural selection.

Populations adapt and evolve by natural selection based on energy availability (choice based on fundamental principles of the provide energy). An example of adaptation and density of the population (the reason for the increase and decrease of the deer population)

Reindeer migrated to Isla Royale, in Lake Superior between Canada and the United States, by swimming or by the lake freezing. After that, the wolves migrated to that island due to the freezing of the lake. The lake has not frozen in recent years. So the population of wolves and reindeer did not migrate in and out. But studies show that in this century, the deer population has fluctuated and has drastically decreased or greatly increased. The reason for this decrease in population is the unfavorable weather and the cold weather and the weakening of the deer, the decrease in food and low access to food sources. With favorable weather and abundance of food, deer population has increased. By feeding wolves on deer, the wolf population has increased and the deer population has decreased. But a balance must be established. Because the population of wolves has increased and the population of deer has decreased. **19(Campbell Biology 2011) Commentary:** In this way, with the decline of the reindeer population, many wolves cannot get their energy and nutrients from deer, so they die and the wolf population decreases. If there is plenty of greens and grass to provide energy and nutrients for the deer, the deer population will increase again. But a balanced cycle is established. Factors such as hunting by wolves and the growth of parasites reduce the deer population again. Deer populations may weaken and disappear due to the occurrence of weather that they are not compatible with, such as cold weather. In cold weather, the feed to supply their energy and nutrients is reduced and deer cannot supply their energy and nutrients. Without providing energy and nutrients, survival and reproduction becomes very difficult and even impossible. Providing energy and nutrients is considered the basic biological rules for success in survival and reproduction. Without energy and nutrients, survival and reproduction is impossible. Natural selection works and selects on the supply of energy and nutrients or failure to supply energy and nutrients.

If the weather is favorable, feed will be abundant, which means that deer will have enough energy and nutrients to survive and reproduce. The resources that provide energy and nutrients to the deer are limited and can only increase the deer population to a certain extent. Parasites get their energy and nutrients from deer. Probably, the density of the deer population has caused the parasite to spread quickly and many deer are killed to provide energy. The deer population is destroyed by the parasite and is decreasing. In this way, the density of the deer population is reduced and the speed of spreading the parasite is also reduced or stopped. The wolf population increases when there is an abundance of biological or biochemical energy, which is the same energy as deer. The wolf population increases, because they get their energy from the large deer population, and this causes the deer population to gradually decrease.

Compatibility and lack of compatibility are related to energy supply and lack of energy supply. That is, those who have the characteristics that can provide their own energy and nutrients, have successful adaptations. On the contrary, those who are not successful in providing energy and nutrients, do not have the proper characteristics and are not successful in providing energy. It should be mentioned in detailed scientific books that success in providing energy and nutrients is an important evolutionary feature that is fundamental and necessary in survival, reproduction and adaptation. Success and failure in providing energy and nutrients are selected by natural selection.

Interpretation of different cellular organelles based on fundamental principles new hypothesis

Structures inside animal cells: (1) Nucleolus (2) Nucleus (3) Ribosome (4) Vesicle (5) Rough endoplasmic reticulum (6) Golgi apparatus (7) Cytoskeleton (8) Smooth endoplasmic reticulum (9) Mitochondria (10) Vacuole (11) Cytoplasm (12) Lysosome (13) Centriole. 31 (Cell Organelles - Types, Structure and their Functions. <https://byjus.com/biology/cell-organelles/>)

https://fa.wikipedia.org/wiki/File%3ABiological_cell.svg

Cell organelles randomly evolved over the years by genetic mutations and natural selection. But natural selection has principles and these cell organelles have been chosen for a specific purpose by the fundamental principles of natural selection.

Here I want to argue and prove that each cell organelle has a specific function, and that is that each cell organelle is a part of basic needs, i.e. providing security, providing energy and nutrients, reproducing or transferring genes to the next generation, and It is responsible for adapting to the environmental conditions of the cell. *I hypothesize that most cellular organelles were selected by natural selection based on the fundamental principles of the new hypothesis. Maybe the selection is done at the molecular level in the cell organelles, in this article I will not discuss the selection at the molecular level. There are many selections at the molecular level. But in this article, I mean selection based on the fundamental principles of the new hypothesis at the level of cells, individuals and populations. Here, I prove by reasoning that it can be guessed from the function, role and duty of these cellular organelles that they were selected by natural selection, directly or indirectly, based on the fundamental principles of the new hypothesis.*

1-Some cellular organelles were screened and selected by natural selection based on the fundamental principles of provide energy and nutrient.

The cell needs nutrients and energy supply and energy conversion (metabolism). For this purpose, evolution has caused cells to have structures and organelles to absorb and obtain and convert nutrients and food in order to produce energy.

Mitochondria: Plants and animals need organelles called mitochondria to convert food into energy and carry out metabolism in their cells. Plants obtain their energy through photosynthesis. Plants need chlorophyll to make and react with their food. Chlorophyll is a chemical found in the leaves and stems

of almost all plants. The function of chlorophyll is photosynthesis, which means it combines carbon dioxide in the air with water drawn up by plant roots in the presence of light to produce sugars (carbohydrates) and oxygen. Mitochondria use aerobic respiration to produce ATP energy molecules. There is considerable evidence for the evolution of mitochondria from aerobic bacteria. 20(Campbell Biology 2011)

Lysosome: The lysosome is emerging as a signaling hub that can integrate and relay external and internal nutritional information to promote cellular and organismal homeostasis, as well as a major contributor to the processing of energy-dense molecules like glycogen and triglycerides. The lysosome functions in the process of sending signals to other organs and tissues to ensure energy and nutrients. The lysosome controls cells energy and nutrients. 21(Vinod K. Mony, Shawna Benjamin & Eyleen J. O'Rourke 2016) Lysosome a bag that contains many enzymes to break down food and provide energy.

Vesicle: Vesicles can help transport materials that an organism needs to survive and recycle waste materials (provide energy and nutrients). They can also absorb and destroy toxic substances and pathogens to prevent cell damage and infection (provide security). Vesicles also help store and transport materials such as proteins, enzymes, hormones, and neurotransmitters. They are a small but essential part of biological systems and processes such as: digestion and metabolism, the nervous system, kidney and liver function(for provide energy and nutrients). 22(Jenna Lester, Joanne Lewsley 2020) Vesicle is a bag that plays a role in transporting nutrients and provide energy.

Endoplasmic reticulum: The endoplasmic reticulum is a membrane-bound organelle in cells of eukaryotic cells involved in protein synthesis, lipid synthesis, and calcium storage. There are two types of endoplasmic reticulum — the rough and the smooth type. The rough endoplasmic reticulum consists of flattened sacs and is where you will typically find ribosomes attached to its surface, thus, giving it a rough appearance under the microscope. The smooth endoplasmic reticulum, in turn, consists of tubules and vesicles and has a rather smooth appearance because ribosomes do not typically attach to its surface. 23(Site source: Biology Online) The endoplasmic reticulum (ER) has many different functions. These include the translocation of proteins (such as secretory proteins) across the ER membrane; the integration of proteins into the membrane; the folding and modification of proteins in the ER lumen; the synthesis of phospholipids and steroids on the cytosolic side of the ER membrane; and the storage of calcium ions in the ER lumen and their regulated release into the cytosol, reviewed in Matlack et al., 1998; Meldolesi and Pozzan, 1998; Ma and Hendershot, 2001; McMaster, 2001. Quoted from 24(Gia K Voeltz, Melissa M Rolls, Tom A Rapoport 2002)

Interpretation; The endoplasmic reticulum has various functions. But the most important ones related to the new hypothesis are the making and shaping of proteins. The most important function of protein is to build cell components, to build tissues and body parts of organisms. The components of the cell, such as the cell wall, help to supply energy and nutrients to the cell by providing the diffusion of nutrients into the cell. Proteins make up many of the main components of the cell, whose job is to supply the cell with energy and nutrients. Different proteins make body parts such as liver, spleen, stomach and intestines. Stomach, intestines and liver are responsible for supplying energy to the body. Spleen is a part of the immune system that is responsible for the security of the body.

Making proteins in the endoplasmic reticulum requires energy and nutrients. In the energy cycle, the cell can convert proteins, carbohydrates, and lipids back into energy and nutrients. 25(Campbell Biology 2011) Certainly, natural selection has selected the endoplasmic reticulum based on the fundamental principles of providing energy and nutrients and providing security. Perhaps other selections at the molecular level are carried out by natural selection. But my discussion in this article about The selection is based on the fundamental principles of the new hypothesis.

Vacuole: vacuole is a membrane-bound structure in the cytoplasm of a cell that's primarily involved in various biological processes, such as intracellular secretion, excretion, storage, and digestion. It is surrounded by a single membrane and contains various substances. Vacuoles for osmoregulation, for instance, contain water, ions, and other molecules. In plant cells wherein vacuoles are relatively large, the vacuole maintains internal hydrostatic pressure inside the cell and thereby helps plants by providing support to plant structures such as leaves and flowers. As a protective container, it can hold and isolate waste products and other harmful materials from other cellular components. The vacuole also serves as storage. For example, vacuoles of seed store proteins essential for seed germination. [26\(site source: biology\)](#) Vacuoles play roles in provide of nutrient recycling and allocation. They is a place to store water, food for provide energy and nutrients, store excrement for provide security cell, and also regulates the amount of water for provide energy and nutrients the cell. Pigments in the cell vacuole protect from harmful light, provideing security the cell.

Golgi apparatus: This organelle lies at the heart of the secretory pathway and performs numerous functions including modification of secretory cargoes and their sorting and delivery to various destinations, which may be inside or outside the cell. The Golgi apparatus has a characteristic structure that is conserved amongst nearly all eukaryotes, comprising flattened membrane discs called cisternae that are layered on top of each other to generate the Golgi stack. Most 'lower' eukaryotes contain one or more discrete Golgi stacks per cell, while in vertebrates the stacks are typically linked to form the Golgi ribbon, a single copy structure usually found next to the centrosome. [27\(Martin Lowe 2011\)](#)

Interpretation; small bags whose job is to package and distribute nutrients and provide energy in the cell and also outside the cell. Collagen secretes an enzyme that helps the cell to metabolize more easily.

Chloroplasts: exist only in plant cells and their task is to make and store energy or food such as starch, fat and protein. Chloroplasts are responsible for photosynthesis or energy production in plants. In fact, sunlight, which is converted into chemical energy by plants, is the source of energy for all organisms. [28\(Campbell Biology 2011\)](#) interpretation; Different plants evolved by natural selection based on the supply of energy and nutrients in different parts of the world. Some aquatic plants can absorb their energy and materials from salt water and some from fresh water. Some plants in humid areas, Some evolved in mountainous areas, some in desert areas. Their evolution and adaptation by natural selection was based on the way and methods of providing energy and nutrients.

With these interpretations, we reach this conclusion; The fact that cells evolved to have organelles to provide energy and nutrients indicates that mutations have occurred that help provide energy and nutrients to the cell. These mutations were selected by natural selection based on the principles of energy and nutrient supply and accumulated and preserved throughout history. Of course, in some organisms, the way to provide energy and nutrients is different, and this is because natural selection has created different adaptations based on the type of resources for providing energy, the amount of access to energy and nutrients, and other reasons. For example, some plants use sunlight and carbon dioxide to provide energy. Some, like herbivores, exploit plants for their energy and nutrients. Some, like carnivores, eat herbivores for energy and nutrients.

2-Selection of cellular organelles by natural selection based on fundamental principles of provide security

Plasma membrane: ensures the safety of the cell by enclosing the contents of the cell and protecting its constituent organs from external harmful factors. This same cell membrane plays a vital role in regulating the movement of nutrients into the cell to provide energy and remove toxic substances and wastes that the cell does not need and may endanger the cell's safety. The plasma membrane consists of two layers of phospholipids. [29\(Campbell Biology 2011\)](#)

According to the scientists' theory, the early RNA was accidentally trapped inside a bubble (Protocell). 30(Dawkins 1976) This cell wall was adopted by natural selection. Because it leads to more security and thus more cell survival. Inside the cell, there are enzymes to destroy invaders and remove substances harmful for provide security the cell. In addition to the above, the cytoplasm also contains pigments such as melanin, which leads to the formation of color in the pigmented cells of the skin. These pigments protect the cell and the internal structure of the body against the harmful effects of the sun's ultraviolet rays.

Lysosome: Lysosomes are ubiquitous membrane-bound intracellular organelles with an acidic interior. They are central for degradation and recycling of macromolecules delivered by endocytosis, phagocytosis, and autophagy. 31(Hann Appelqvist, Petra Wäster, Katarina Kågedal, Karin Öllinger 2013) One of the organelles of the cell is responsible for the provide security of the cell. The lysosome is responsible for secreting enzymes to destroy pathogenic and incapacitating agents.

The organs that protect the cell against invaders were created during evolution. These cellular organs were selected and maintained by natural selection based on the fundamental principles of security. Any feature that leads to the security of cells is maintained and supported by natural selection. With this evidence, we conclude that security is one of the basic needs of cells. Because it is not possible for the cell to survive and multiply without ensuring its security. If the cell does not have defense, security and protection structures, it will be destroyed by attackers. Even security has changed in organisms during evolution, and natural selection preserves and supports Compatiblea and fitness options in the best possible way to ensure the security of organisms.

3-Selection of cell organelles by natural selection based on their own reproduction and transfer of genes to the next generation

The cell needs to multiply, reproduce(reproduction) and grow.

Nucleus: Contains DNA (hereditary material) as well as various proteins and the nucleolus.

Ribosomes: are small organelles that contain RNA and specific proteins in the cytoplasm. Inside the cell, ribosomes are directly involved in building proteins using their RNA and amino acids. This process involves decoding the information contained in mRNA and using amino acids to produce the required proteins. 32(Campbell Biology 2011) All cells require the DAN translation process for their reproduce. Cell division or cell proliferation plays a vital role in survival and meeting (provide) the needs of cells and large organisms. In this way, there are cells with various functions in the organism that multiply regularly and replace old cells to meet the fundamental and diverse needs of organisms (energy, security, etc.).

There are some enzymes in the cell that help the reproduction and multiplication of the cell. Cells need to reproduce to survive. What led me to the fact that cell reproduction is one of the needs of cell fundamental was that it is impossible for a cell to survival without replicating itself. Cell division is different in eukaryotic cells. Cells divide in two ways, meiosis and mitosis. Cell division has different stages. What is important is that without cell division, the continued survival of organisms will be compromised. In the act for reproduced, genes carefully copy and replicate cell organelles. For cell proliferation, there is a need for cell organelles and necessary materials.

4- The cell needs to move. But, why did movement in cells evolve and be selected for by natural selection?

Some cells, such as sperm cells, have organelles called flagella for cell motility. Many single-celled and microscopic organisms are also motile, using methods such as flagellar motility, amoeboid movement, gliding motility, and swarming motility. It is now widely accepted that the basic engine for gliding or

crawling locomotion is the actin cytoskeleton. ³³(TJ Mitchison, LP Cramer 1996) Cell motility or migration is an essential cellular process for a variety of biological events. During embryonic development, cells migrate to appropriate locations for the morphogenesis of tissues and organs. Cells need to migrate to heal the wound in repairing damaged tissue. Vascular endothelial cells (Ecs) migrate to form new capillaries during angiogenesis. White blood cells migrate to the sites of inflammation to kill bacteria. Cell migration is a multistep process that involves the integration and coordination of complex biochemical and biomechanical signals. ³⁴(Song Li, Jun-Lin Guan, Shu Chien 2005) Directed, purposeful movement is one of the qualities that we most closely associate with living organisms, and essentially all known forms of life on this planet exhibit some type of self-generated movement or motility. Even organisms that remain sessile most of the time, like flowering plants and trees, are quite busy at the cellular level, with large organelles, including chloroplasts, constantly racing around within cellular boundaries. Directed biological movement requires that the cell be able to convert its abundant stores of chemical energy into mechanical energy. ³⁵(Daniel A Fletcher, Julie A Theriot 2004)

Motility was selected and choice by natural selection because motility helps cells provide energy and secure themselves. A cell that moves can better obtain energy and nutrients and provide security. There is competition for energy supply, security, reproduction and finally adaptation to environmental conditions among individuals of the same species and between species. Those with better mobility help them to succeed in the competition for provide energy and nutrients, provide security, and reproduction. Eventually they succeed in survival and gene transfer. Also, 1- cells such as red blood cells help to supply energy to different body tissues of organisms by carrying oxygen and moving with the help of blood flow inside the body of organisms. Selection based on providing energy and nutrients 2- Some cells, such as white blood cells, help the safety of organisms by moving towards harmful substances (providing security). Selection based on providing security 3- Movement helps cells like sperm to move towards the egg and reproduce. Selection based on the transfer of genes to the next generation.

An example of selection on the basis of energy and nutrient supply

Darwin's Galápagos bird beak interpretation

In the Galapagos Islands, Darwin observed four types of finches with different beaks. But why are there four types of finches with different beaks in the Galapagos Islands?

Galapagos finches are definitely one of the most famous examples of evolution, and their name will forever be associated with Charles Darwin's journey and his theory of natural selection. Due to the variety of beak size and shape, each species is adapted to a specific type of food. *Geospiza* has a thick beak that is adapted for eating hard seeds. *Camarhynchus pallidus* even uses cactus spines and thin tree branches to pull arthropods out of tree holes. **36(What is evolution?, Ernst Meyer)** Suppose there are two types of finches (Darwin's finches) Galapagos finches on an island, each of which obtains the energy and nutrients it needs from different sources. For example, one type of bird uses insects and another uses plant seeds for provide energy and nutrients.

https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/File:3ADarwin%27s_finches.jpeg

Interpretation of Galapagos birds' beaks based on the principles of the new hypothesis; Evolution and natural selection work on bird beaks in different environments, changing the shape of birds' beaks based on their energy and nutrient needs. (I just remind you that changing the shape of the beak to provide energy and nutrition is only one example of the traits that provide energy to organisms. In order to provide energy, in addition to changing the beak, there must be changes in the intestines, stomach, metabolism, thermal balance of the body and...) If an island has plant food sources that produce large seeds and other food sources such as insects are limited, finches with large and strong beaks will survive and reproduce. But why? Finches that have this large beak are better able to break the seeds and eat its contents and are less likely to starve. Therefore, this type of bird can provide the energy and nutrients it needs by breaking hard seeds with its large beak. But finches that feed on insects cannot supply their energy and nutrients due to the lack of insects. Therefore, those who can only feed on insects, their population will decrease or disappear completely.

On the other hand, the second island has abundant food sources of insects, and scarce sources of plant seeds to provide finches with energy and nutrients. On the second island, any creature that can provide its own energy survives. Evidence obtained from Darwin's research showed that finch birds with narrow and sharp beaks, survive and reproduce more on this island where there are many insects. **37(What is evolution? Ernst Meyer)** The reason is that there are many insects on this island. They have narrow and sharp beaks, they can hunt insects better and are less hungry. According to the principles of the new hypothesis, they survive because they can get the energy and nutrients they need from insects. Over time, these different patterns of energy supply based on beak shape (as a heritable trait) can change the beak shape of any population. For example, population the first island may have been selected by the principle of energy supply and moved towards larger and stronger beaks to obtain their energy from plant seeds. Because in this island, only this type is able to provide its own energy and nutrients. Selection based on provide energy and nutrient would have made the population of the second island have thinner and sharper beaks to provide their energy from insects and only this type would survive. Finally, it appears that the two populations or two types of finches are somewhat different.

Total resulting; In fact, those Galapagos birds that did not survive and died, before associating them with survival and reproduction, if we look more carefully, they were selected by natural selection because they did not have the proper characteristics to provide energy and nutrients. Their beaks could not provide food and energy. This issue should not be related only to survival and reproduction. The reason for those that managed to survive and reproduce is that all these birds had a special beak to supply their energy. One to eat insects and another by pulling insects out of trees or another to break

the hard seeds of plants. Evolution on energy and nutrients is any small gradual beneficial change that leads to adaptation to provide energy and nutrients in its general sense.

Important point: Beak, digestive system and in general the metabolic system of birds, even the wings, the size of the bird, the quality and quantity of resources for providing energy, access to different resources, distance from resources, environmental conditions such as; Heat and cold and humidity, wind, access to water and oxygen, type of food, amount of food, hardness and softness of food, ingredients of food, amount of body needs, body size and many other things related to provide energy and nutrients, that it affects the formation and development of organs.

This hypothesis answers the question much better than previous theories, why are the beaks of Darwin's Galapagos birds different? Each beak adapted to a specific type of food to provide energy and nutrients. Here the same Darwinian laws apply, beneficial changes that lead to provide energy and nutrients are maintained by natural selection, thus driving evolution. Those whose body parts are able to provide energy in the above environmental conditions will survive and the rest will die because they have body parts and traits that cannot provide their own energy and nutrients. This process leads to successful survival and creation of new species. Fundamental principles of provide energy and nutrient have led to changing populations. If enough time passes, due to the accumulation of changes in traits and characteristics, body parts and behavior to provide energy and nutrient, natural selection produces certain species in a certain environment. The bird needs energy and nutrients to carry out the process of anabolism and catabolism (getting energy and nutrients to build and reproduce cellular components and organic molecules). He must consume food to have energy and nutrients. Food is usually taken in through the mouth. The bird must eat the food (break and eat) and send it to its stomach. All kinds of bird's beaks are suitable for all kinds food such: insect , tree fruits, tree kernels and plant seeds. Plant seeds and some foods are hard and must be broken and eaten and enter the stomach.

The choice based on the useful features of provide security, causes evolution and adaptation

One of the principles of natural selection is provide security. Sometimes, even though the cells or organisms have high reproduction, they die before reaching reproductive age. Because it cannot provide its own security. Example; Fish that give birth to many children. But because the fish eggs or their small children are eaten by predators, that means the children or fish eggs cannot ensure their security against predators. Or their security and safety is weak. (or they cannot get enough food and nutrients to supply their energy) they die before reaching reproductive age. So their survival will be difficult and impossible because they cannot provide their security.

There are other cells and organisms that reproduce less than the above example. But due to the defensive enzyme or cell wall and other cellular defense organs, the descendants of these have better security and survive and reproduce. If we define cell security; The security of the cell means that the cell has a cell wall, harmful substances do not enter the cell, the cell is not damaged. Or the cell has a defense enzyme that if unknown and harmful substances enter the cell, they identify them and destroy them and ensure the safety of the cell. Various behaviors have evolved to ensure their own security in living organisms. Such as behaviors that have ways to escape, hide and blend in with the environment to protect and secure themselves from the eyes of enemies.

Immunity (providing security) is divided into two groups: inherent immunity and adaptive immunity. Most organisms have innate immunity, but some have adaptive immunity. Host responses against invading pathogens are the basic physiological responses of all living organisms. Since the emergence

of the first eukaryotic cells, a series of defense mechanisms have evolved to ensure cellular integrity, homeostasis, and host survival. Invertebrates, from protozoans to metazoans, have cellular receptors that bind to foreign elements and distinguish self from non-self. This ability in multicellular animals is accompanied by the presence of phagocytes with different names (ombocyte, hemocyte, coelomocyte) in different groups, including animal sponges, worms, fish, molluscs, crustaceans, insects and urchins (sea). 38(Kurt Buchmann, 2014) commentary; A response against pathogens is necessary to ensure and provide the safety of organisms. If there is no defense mechanism in organisms, survival of organisms will be difficult or even impossible. Natural selection preserves any changes and mutations that aid survival. Adaptations and evolutionary changes that lead to provide security are selected and maintained by natural selection, ultimately contributing to survival.

Approximately 500 million years ago, two types of neo-combined adaptive immune systems appeared in vertebrates. 39(Zeev Pancer., Max D. Cooper, 2006) The evolutionary emergence of vertebrates was accompanied by major morphological and functional innovations, including the development of an adaptive immune system. Vertebrate adaptive immunity is based on the clonal expression of somatic diversifying antigen receptors on lymphocytes. This is a common feature of both jawless and jawed vertebrates, although these two groups of extant vertebrates use different structural types of antigen receptors and the main mechanisms for their somatic diversity. These observations suggest that the common vertebrate ancestor must have already possessed a complex immune system, including B and T lymphocyte lineages and primitive lymphoid organs such as the thymus, but probably lacked the facilities for somatic diversification of antigen receptors. Interestingly, memory formation, previously considered a defining feature of adaptive immunity, also occurs in the context of innate immune responses and can even be observed in unicellular organisms, testifying to the convergent evolutionary history of aspects of Adaptive safety is distinctive. 40(Thomas Boehm, Jeremy B. Swan, Annu. Rev. Anim. Biosci., 2014)

Interpretation; The evolution of the adaptive immune system in vertebrates represents an advance in provide security that has been selected by natural selection directly based on the principle of provide security. Natural selection selects and maintains more adaptive methods and traits that are useful and better ensure the safety of vertebrates. Beneficial traits and alleles or phenotypes that help provide security, or provide security better than competitors, lead to victory in the struggle for survival against competitors and are passed on to the next generation.

The cellular immune response of insects is mediated by specialized blood cells that employ germline encoded receptors to recognize, engulf, and eliminate microbes through the process of phagocytosis. Phagocytosis is a vital component of innate immunity and research over the past 3 decades in model systems, such as the fruit fly *Drosophila melanogaster* and mosquitoes, has led to the identification of an array of processes that invertebrates rely on to respond to invading microorganisms. 41(Ashley E. Nazario-Toole, Louisa P. Wu 2017)

The following example shows how providing security as a fundamental principle is selected by natural selection and causes evolution, adaptation and survival.

The skin color of many animals is similar to the environment. This makes them hidden from the eyes of others, especially rivals and enemies. Since living organisms have different colors to hide in the environment, color change has been developed based on adaptation to the environment. Animals that protected themselves better than others lived longer and reproduced more than their competitors.

In this example, two groups of mice live in a new area with black rocks due to a genetic mutation with inherited variation in coat or skin color, one black mice and the other yellowish brown mice. In this environment with black earthy stones, birds of prey recognize brown mice better than black mice

among black stones. Since brown mice are easily seen by birds of prey, large numbers of brown mice are hunted and far fewer black mice are hunted. In this way, the proportion of black mice in the population increases.

Image on the left: A population of rats has entered or spawned in an area where the surrounding rocks are very dark. As a result of natural genetic variation, some of these mice are black and some are brown. The picture on the left shows that the population of brown and black mice is equal. The middle image shows that brown mice are more visible to birds of prey and less secure. Therefore, brown mice are eaten more often than black mice. The image on the right shows only the remaining black mice that managed to secure themselves (provide security) better than the brown mice. Mice whose immunity is provided for any reason reach reproductive age and produce children. Therefore, based on the fundamental principles of selection based on providing security, the abundance of black mice will increase in the next generation.

Coat color is an inherited trait in all organisms. A trait that can be passed from parent to child, so an increase in the proportion of black mice in the remaining population means an increase in the proportion of black mice in the next generation. After several generations through selection based on safety, the population may consist entirely of black mice. This change in population has occurred by natural selection because black mice provide better security. Mouse color, which leads to better or less security, is a heritable trait that causes variation in populations. An important point to pay attention to is that sometimes useful traits or organs and behaviors provide energy and security in an environment with special conditions and are desirable in this environment. But the same traits may not be useful in another environment and may even be harmful to some organisms. In the sense that they cannot provide his energy and security.

In the example of black and yellow mice mentioned above, the reason why black mice become more abundant than brown mice in successive generations is not because they are more evolved. Rather, it is because they have an inherited trait that allows them to secure themselves (provide security) in that environment. This makes the rats last longer and reproduce in that particular environment (black earth). In a different environment, for example, where the color of the stones is bright and white or yellow, it is possible to change the position of favorable and unfavorable attributes. That is, in this environment, black mice are hunted more and white and yellow mice are hunted less. This causes the proportion of yellow and white mice to increase in the population. Because they were able to provide security in this special environment. Therefore, more yellow and white mice reproduce more because of provide security. Many offspring of rats use these useful traits that protect them in that particular environment. Therefore, their children will increase and pass on useful features to the next generation. We should note that in this environment with the stones is bright and white or yellow, white and yellow mice can not only be more secure, but also have more provide energy, reproduction and movement.

Interpretation of the reason for the abundance of black moths in the industrial era of England

The rapid spread of a novel black form (known as carbonaria) of the peppered moth *Biston betularia* in 19th-century Britain is a textbook example of how an altered environment may produce morphological

adaptation through genetic change. 42(Arjen E van't Hof, Nicola Edmonds, Martina Dalíková, František Marec, Ilik J Saccheri 2011)

From the beginning, several reasons have been proposed for changes in melanic gene frequency in pepper moth *Biston betularia* and other industrial melanic moths. These include the higher innate fitness of melanic forms and selective predation for camouflage. The existence and possible origin of the heterozygous advantage is discussed. Since the 1950s, as a result of empirical evidence, selective predation has become the preferred explanation and is undoubtedly the main cause of frequency change. 43(LM Cook, Ilik J Saccheri 2013)

Interpretation of the cause of abundance of black butterfly based on the fundamental principles of the new hypothesis; The trees were darkened due to the smoke caused by the industrial revolution. The black butterfly is well camouflaged among the black soot and is rarely hunted by birds. But The white butterfly is easier to see among the black soot and is hunted by birds. The black butterfly in the midst of black soot provides better security than the white butterfly. This shows the importance of providing security. The survival of the black butterfly has been selected based on providing security. The black butterfly has been more successful in securing itself. A white butterfly can not camouflage in a dark place. Therefore, his security is not provide and he is easily removed by natural selection.

Another example of adaptation, evolution and selection based on the fundamental principles of providing energy and nutrients

Bedbugs feed on seeds inside fruits with their proboscis, which is a kind of hollow rod or tube. In South Florida, the bed bug *Jadera haematoloma* feeds on the seeds of a native ivy called *Cardiospermum corindom*. But in central Florida, these ivy and seeds became scarce. Therefore, in this area, today, bed bugs had to feed on a tree imported from Asia called *Koelreuteria elegans*. Bedbugs generally feed best when the length of their proboscis is proportional to the distance between the seed and the surface of the fruit. The fruit seed of *Koelreuteria elegans* consists of three broad segments. The seed of *Koelreuteria elegans* tree is closer to the surface of the fruit than the seed of ivy tree. University researchers predicted that natural selection would cause the proboscis of those that feed on the seeds of the tree fruit to be shorter than those that feed on the seeds of the ivy tree. In fact, the population that feeds on the fruit of the tree has a shorter proboscis. Studies have confirmed the researchers' predictions. The researchers examined the evolution of snout length in other similar places, such as Australia, Louisiana, and Oklahoma. Here the bed bug's population had started feeding on the newly imported trees. The seed in the fruit of the new trees had a greater distance from the fruit surface than the native trees. Therefore, the researchers predicted that natural selection would increase the length of the proboscis. Studies have confirmed this prediction. 44(Campbell Biology 2011)

Interpretation of the reason for the adaptation and selection of the length of the bed bug's proboscis based on the fundamental principles of providing energy and nutrients; This type of bed bug feeds on the seeds inside the fruit to provide the energy and nutrients it needs. The natural selection selects the bed bug proboscis that can reach the fruit seed and succeed in supplying its energy and nutrients from the fruit seed. The proboscis of bed bugs is selected based on the fundamental principles of providing energy and nutrients. If the bedbugs proboscis is of the right size (neither long nor short) that it manages to supply its energy and nutrients from the contents of the fruit seed, this proboscis will be accepted by natural selection. Therefore, when the distance between the fruit and the seed is large, a long proboscis is needed to reach the seed in order to successfully supply energy and nutrients. And on the contrary, if the distance between the seed and the surface of the fruit is small, it needs a short proboscis to supply

its energy and nutrients. Here it becomes clear that the length of the proboscis is selected based on the success in providing energy and nutrients.

We should not forget that genetic mutations cause different bug proboscis, natural selection only selects them based on the basic principles of providing energy and nutrients.

Another example of selection by natural selection based on the fundamental principles of security supply and energy supply.

I show here that successful adaptations are selected by natural selection based on success in providing energy and providing security. Mr. Darwin says; On the mother island, there are strong winds that blow winged insects into the sea. Insects of the same type found in other parts of the world with wings are the same type of insects on this island without wings. Environmental conditions have made the ratio of wingless insects to be higher than winged insects. Wingless insects exist on the islands as a result of natural selection and disuse. Call it a combination of disuse and natural selection. ⁴⁵(Darwin 1859)

New interpretation; But the more correct theory is that their lack of wings was chosen based on the principles of providing security. The wind threatens the security of the insect. Those that had wings on this island were blown into the sea by the wind. Now some of this type of insect became wingless, those who didn't have wings, their safety is ensured. Because those without wings were not blown into the sea by the wind. So they didn't need wings. Or rather, on this island, all those insects that are thrown into the sea by the wind disappeared. But changes appeared in a wingless insect. This insect is not thrown into the sea by the wind and their number has increased in this island. The wings threatened the security of these insects. It means that those who had wings were not safe. Insects without wings were more secure. In these organisms, security has been selected for, and wingless insects evolved on this island.

[The evolution of flight in organisms has been selected by natural selection for the purpose of providing energy.](#)

Darwin mentions that on some of these islands, these same insects feed on flowers (get their energy from flowers), not only have wings not disappeared, but they have evolved. ⁴⁶(Darwin 1859) According to the basic principles of the new hypothesis, because these insects get their energy from flowers, they need to move with wings and fly to reach the flowers. Therefore, through the basic mechanism of natural selection, evolution has favored winged locomotion for provide energy in these insects. Success in energy provision is selected by natural selection.

[Selection at the beginning of life by natural selection based on the supply of energy and nutrients/ evolution at the beginning of life based on the supply of energy and nutrients.](#)

The chemical compatibility of sulfur and its abundance in prebiotic Earth as reduced sulfide (H₂S) have made it a source of life 3.8 billion years ago and also the main source of early evolutionary energy. A dramatic increase in ambient oxygen about 600 million years ago led to the end of H₂S as an energy source, and H₂S-dependent animals either became extinct, displaced, or adapted to sulfide energy. The simplest definition of life is the ability to use and control energy. Today, almost all the energy of life

comes from the sun. Plants oxidize water to oxygen and reduce inorganic carbon, while animals obtain energy by reversing this process. 47(Kenneth R. Olson, Karl D. Straub (2015)

interpretation; I interpret the above in a new way that better explains the evolution of the first organisms. H₂S has been the most primitive source of energy for life. 600 million years ago, evolution took place and the adaptation for providing energy changed to oxygen. Remember that natural selection only selected this new adaptation 600 million years ago to improve energy supply. Oxygen than H₂S can produce more ATP for energy. Selection was based on energy supply and these changes and mutations were accepted.

The emergence of life on early Earth required the presence of at least three different substances and related physical properties: liquid water, a source of free energy (need for energy), and organic compounds capable of self-assembly (need for reproduction). Liquid water is essential for all primitive and modern life, and existence of life in the absence of water is very impossible. Potential energy sources for life include sunlight and energy from chemical imbalances in underwater or underground sites. Self-assembling compounds must be available to form building blocks for polymer synthesis and formation of boundary structures. Perhaps the most important definition of life is that the entire molecular system must be able to reproduce itself using genetically encoded self-assembly of components and polymerization reactions. In a population of reproductive systems competing for energy and nutrients (competition for energy supply), changes cause changes in individual molecular systems that affect growth and reproductive efficiency. A population of finite molecular systems can then be subjected to the kinds of selection processes required for Darwinian evolution. The essential role of membrane boundaries is to create a selective permeability barrier that is necessary to separate the cytoplasm from the external environment. (Cell membranes help provide security by keeping out enemies and harmful substances, and help provide energy and cellular metabolism by facilitating the entry of nutrients.) All of these functions require membrane-associated proteins that may be present in primitive forms. Thus, it appears that the membrane boundaries of primary cells simply form a selective permeability barrier that allows essential nutrients (substances needed for provide energy and nutrients) to pass through but retains the primary biosynthetic polymer products...In a population of reproductive systems competing for energy and nutrients, changes induce changes in individual molecular systems that affect growth and reproductive efficiency. 48(Alain Monnard, David W. Deamer- 2002)

interpretation; The contents in parentheses are my interpretation based on the fundamental principles of the new hypothesis. The most important point is that selection based on the provision of energy and nutrients has existed since the beginning of life and has led to the creation of different methods of providing energy and nutrients. This shows how important natural selection is to the selection of energy and nutrient supply for adaptation, survival and reproduction. Materials to provide the energy used for self-replication have focused on quantitative chemistry. The evolution was gradually towards adaptation of more efficient sources for energy supply. It has been mentioned in the above that the competition for energy supply has been intense. Therefore, some may not have been able to provide their energy. Their removal was only due to the failure of energy supply. It is better to explain Darwin's selection process mentioned above on the basis of energy supply from now on.

Interpretation of some of Mr. Richard Dawkins' theories based on the fundamental principles of the new hypothesis

In The Selfish Gene book, Mr. Dawkins says: "Experiments were set up where rats were put together in a box. They put a lot of food there. The birth rate increased and the population became very large. But after some time the population of mice started to decrease. "The researchers found that female mice regulated their reproduction with the amount of resources and food." 49(The selfish gene 1976)

interpretation based on the fundamental principles of the new hypothesis; Female mice measure the amount of food and resources that can be needed to provide energy for themselves, provide energy for

their children, and provide energy for the whole group; and regulate itself reproduction. If females do not do this, natural selection can adjust the reproductive rate of the population by selecting based on the supply of energy and nutrients. In this way, natural selection adjusts the mouse population by removing some children and individuals from the mouse population who cannot provide themselves with energy and nutrients due to the problem of lack of resources and food. Natural selection goes so far that only those who can provide their own energy and nutrients remain. Now there is a population left that has resources and food to provide its energy and nutrients. Regulation of rat populations is selected by natural selection based on provide energy and nutrient availability.

Mr. Dawkins says in the book *River out of Eden*: When a monkey (gorilla) falls from a tree, some of them have strong bones and remain healthy. But some break their arms or legs. Monkeys use their hands more, that's why their hand bones are big and strong, but not their legs. If they break a leg when they fall from a tree, it's not a big issue for natural selection, because the monkey needs more hands. The monkey eats with his hands, climbs the tree and finds shelter and food with his hands. Natural selection has accumulated beneficial changes in the bones of the hand, creating a strong hand so that it does not break easily when falling from a tree. It is more likely that those with weak hand bones broke their hands when they fell from the tree and had difficulty climbing the tree for food, mating and shelter. Therefore, they could not survive and pass on their genes. 50(Richard Dawkins 1995)

But how does the principles of the new hypothesis explain the resistance of strong bones? The monkey hands are selected and choice based on the fundamental principles of the new hypothesis.

If a monkey (gorilla) falls from a tree and his hand remains healthy due to having strong bones, in fact the monkey can still use his hands 1- (hand choice) to provide energy and food, 2- (hand selected) to provide security and protection From oneself against enemies and rivals, 3- Climbing the tree by hand during rain, cold and heat, choosing to adapt to the environmental conditions. 4- Finally, this monkey can go to the top of the tree with healthy hands and find a mate and reproduce. (Selection based on the transfer of genes to the next generation). He passes it on to his children. But monkeys that fall from trees and break their arms and legs are likely to fail to obtain and supply energy and food, provide security, reproduce, and adapt to environmental conditions. If an organism cannot provide its energy and nutrients and security, does not adapt to environmental conditions, does not succeed in transferring genes to the next generation, it will be eliminated by natural selection. Or 1- So they may die of starvation or lack of energy and nutrients. 2- An animal with a broken arm will be easily killed by hunters, in other words, lack of security. 3- In case of rain and flood or cold and heat, this monkey with a broken hand has little chance to find shelter and cannot adapt to the environmental conditions. 4- Therefore, a monkey with a broken arm and leg has little chance of finding a mate to reproduce and pass on the weak bone characteristics to the next generation.

Interpretation of simple eye evolution based on the fundamental principles of the new hypothesis

The simple eye of a seashell can only distinguish darkness from light. But this is enough when he feels a shadow, he clings to the rock, 51(Richard Dawkins 1986) or in other words, provide security himself by clinging to the rocks.

Simple eyes can help in identifying edible materials such as grass and algae,(Richard Dawkins 1986)so that the oyster can better find food to supply its energy and nutrients. This is why natural selection selects simple eyes based on success in providing energy and nutrients and providing security. If the simple eyes manage to provide energy and nutrients and provide security, then they are preserved by natural selection because they are ultimately suitable for the survival and reproduction of the oyster.

Interpretation of one of the theories of Mr. Richard Dawkins from the book *The Selfish Gene* based on the fundamental principles of the new hypothesis

Based on the fundamental principles of the new hypothesis; Parental investment in their offspring or genes has been through investing in providing energy or feeding the offspring. Protecting children is actually the investment of parents to provide energy and nutrients and ensure the safety of children, so that the children's genes, which are copies of the parents' genes, survive.

How do genes that provide energy, nutrients, and provide security spread to future generations and drive evolution?

A female cuckoo spreads her genes by laying eggs in the nests of other birds. Cuckoos have genes for making loud noises. A cuckoo chick attracts the attention of its step-parents by making loud noises to provide energy or food. This sound has evolved in the cuckoo because with this sound can to its provide energy. The sound of the cuckoo chick is selected and choice based on the supply of energy and nutrients. parents have genes that provide them with energy and nutrients when they hear the loud cuckoo or their own chicks. By supplying energy to the cuckoo chick, the loud noise of the cuckoo chick will be reduced and quiet. 52(Richard Dawkins 1976)

In fact, by silencing the cuckoo, they want to ensure the safety of their chicks and the cuckoo they think is their baby. Because the loud noise of the chickens may attract predators and endanger the safety of the chickens. The gene or allele or the behavior of paying attention to noisy chicks is selected and spread among the parents by natural selection based on the principle of provide security. These parents provide noisy chicks with energy and nutrients earlier and more than others, In addition to providing energy, this practice actually provides security to the chickens by keeping them quiet. Birds that did not have this gene most likely did not pay attention to the children who produced loud sounds and did not provide them with energy and nutrients. Therefore, the loud noise attracts the attention of the predators towards the chicks and they are eaten by the predators, the security of the chickens is not provided. Therefore, the gene of not feeding a child who makes loud noises is not reproduced. But the gene that nurtures children who make loud noises is spread. Because by providing energy and nutrients, these children become quiet and do not attract the attention of predators. Therefore, their security is provided by keeping them quiet or supplying them with energy. The gene of the cuckoo chick that produces loud sounds has been spread by natural selection based on the principles of energy supply in the next generation, because it was able to attract the attention of its parents or step parents by producing loud sounds to provide itself with energy.

That cuckoo chick or chicks whose voice was less than this chick, could not attract the attention of the parents or step parents to provide energy. They will probably die of starvation or lack of energy. Therefore, chickens that have a low voice, their genes will not be passed on to the next generation. Those with alleles and phenotypes that are better able to provide energy and nutrients than their competitors survive and reproduce.

Analysis of the behavior of organisms based on the fundamental principles (new hypothesis) of natural selection

Termites, honey bees and common bees, their workers are sterile and do not give birth to young. Based on biology and genetics research, these termites are responsible for protecting the eggs of their siblings to grow. In all living organisms, siblings are likely to have identical copies of the same genes. The environment determines whether the workers become queens or males. Also because these brothers and sisters are the workers' closest genetic relatives and are nearly identical copies of their own genes. For this reason, they take care of their gene copies. 53(Dawkins 1976)

Their division of labor can be interpreted based on the fundamental principles of the new hypothesis. The division of work of bees and termites is done by natural selection based on the fundamental

principles of providing energy and nutrients, providing security and adapting to environmental conditions, and transferring genes to the next generation. 1- For example, some workers are responsible for securing and defending the queen, protecting their siblings, defending the hive, and they protect them at any cost. They will fight to the death with the attackers to ensure the safety (provide security) of their group. 2- Some workers are responsible for the task and mission of bringing food to supply energy and nutrients (water and food) to siblings, queen and other members of the hive. 3- The queen mother and some males are responsible for reproduction and transfer of genes to the next generation.

Interpretation of the selfish gene theory of Professor Richard Dawkins based on the fundamental principles of the new hypothesis

The (selfish) gene reproduces to maximize its survival... Genes are immortal, they came from ancient times... Organisms are the survival machines of genes. Selfishness is a metaphor and genes are not consciously selfish. 54(Richard Dawkins 1976)

If we accept the selfishness of genes metaphorically, then the interpretation of the selfishness of genes is based on the fundamental principles of the new hypothesis; Genes selfishly only care about their energy and nutrients supply. Genes also only care about provide their own security. In this way, in the competition to provide their own energy and nutrients and provide their security, sometimes they don't let others provide itself energy and nutrients and their security. If genes can provide energy and nutrients, and security, they will eventually focus on their ultimate goal, which is reproduction by copying copies of themselves and passing it on to the next generation. Depending on the degree of genetic relatedness, genes may help provide energy and nutrients, provide security, and pass on the genes of their close relatives. That organisms are the survival machines of genes, that is, survival machines are responsible for providing energy and nutrients for genes, providing security for genes, adapting to environmental conditions such as temperature and humidity, etc., copying and transferring genes to the next generation.

Examples of self-sacrifice and selfishness, selected by natural selection to provide energy and nutrients to genetic relatives: when a bee defends a honey or food source with its sting, when it stings an attacker, its sting is removed from its body, He dies after a while. 55(Richard Dawkins 1976) In fact, this bee defends important sources for provide energy and nutrients for its genetic relatives.

Examples of self-sacrifice and selfishness, selected by natural selection to provide security of genetic kin: in the case of a bird that screams when an eagle and another predator approach, warning the group. The bird may die from this. 56(Richard Dawkins 1976) Commentary; With this self-sacrifice, the bird may not be able to provide itself security. But this sacrifice provide security of the group or genetic kin. Natural selection preserves and supports any trait and behavior that leads to securing(provide security) genes.

Interpreting the relationship between plants and herbivores and carnivores in ecology by means of a new hypothesis

In ecology, it should be clearly stated that ecological changes sometimes occur in connection with the fundamental principles of energy and nutrient supply. For example, a change in the level of soil nutrients and a change in light energy can be effective in the multiplication and reproduction of plants. A change in the plant population will bring about a change in the herbivore population. Because herbivores get their energy and nutrients from plants. Also, the change in the population of herbivores, which occurred due to the change in the population of plants, brings about the change in the population of carnivores. Because carnivores get their energy and nutrients from herbivores. In other words, the energy of carnivores depends on herbivores. Also, the energy of herbivores depends on plants. And the energy of plants depends on water, light, nutrients in the soil and carbon dioxide. The relationship between these should be analyzed based on the ability to supply energy from another level. If there are

plenty of nutrients, light, water and any other substances that plants need to provide their energy, the number of reproduction and survival of plants will also increase. If the number of plants increases, the number of herbivores whose energy is provided by plants will also increase through reproduction. In this way, many carnivores can provide their energy and nutrients for reproduction and survival from many herbivores.

Species and populations survive that are better able to provide security than competitors. By better here I mean more consistent.

For example, consider two populations of buffalos, one of which has large and sharp horns for defense. But another population does not have such horns. Hence horns evolved to function as weapons inflicting damage; as defense organs shielding their owner; as binding organs allowing opponents a secure lock in battle; as display organs having an a priori intimidating effect on certain conspecifics. 57(Geist, Valerius 1966) When faced with enemies and hunters, the population, which has large and sharp horns, wounds the attackers to death. Defense with a horns big and sharp, provide their security. But those without big and sharp horns are more likely to be hunted and their population will decrease.

If a small group of buffalos with large and sharp horns migrates to a population that does not have large and sharp horns, they will mix together through gene mixing (reproduction). Genes for large and sharp horns spread in the population. Because this feature has provide their security, it keeps the ones with horns alive and spreads in the population and changes the population. The distribution of the frequency of the sharp horn allele among the population was most likely due to selection based on providing security. Because it provides the security of its owner. Perhaps, in some cases, sexual selection is effective in the frequency of the sharp horn allele.

Here I argue that most human body parts are probably selected and evolved by natural selection based on the basic principles of the new hypothesis (Basic Principles of Natural Selection – Basic Principles of Biological).

The human body consists of various major organ systems, each composed of different organs and tissues that work together as a functional unit. Some of the main components and functions of each system are summarized below.(1) A: The integumentary system, composed of the skin and associated structures, protects the body from invasion by harmful microorganisms and chemicals. 58(Chuong et al 2002) ;based on fundamental principles biological of new hypothesis, skin provide security of human body_ B: it also prevents water loss from, the water important for provide energy of human body.

(2) The musculoskeletal system (also referred to separately as the muscle system and the skeletal system), composed of the skeletal muscles and bones (with about 206 of the latter in adults), moves the body and protectively houses its internal organs. Movement, the intricate cooperation of muscle and nerve fibres, is the means by which an organism interacts with its environment. The innervation of muscle cells, or fibres, permits an animal to carry out the normal activities of life. An organism must move to find food or, if it is sedentary, must have the means to bring food to itself. An animal must be able to move nutrients and fluids through its body, and it must be able to react to external or internal stimuli. Muscle cells fuel their actions by converting chemical energy in the form of adenosine triphosphate (ATP), which is derived from the metabolism of food, into mechanical energy. 59(Albrecht von Haller A.V. Hill Jean-Martin Charcot Hugh Esmor Huxley Giovanni Alfonso Borelli.[Encyclopedia Britannica; 2023) The human musculoskeletal system, like other organisms, provides its various basic needs. Musculoskeletal system helps people move with the help of muscles in their legs. A: Movement helps a lot to get food or provide energy and accordingly it has evolved in humans. B: It is also important to move to escape from enemies and provide security. C: Moving to

find a sexual partner to reproduce and transfer genes to the next generation. D: movement to adapt to environmental conditions; For example, moving to a hot or cold environment, human migration from a cold environment in winter to a temperate environment, or migration in summer to a cooler environment, which has evolved in humans to adapt to environmental conditions.

(3) The respiratory system, composed of the breathing passages, lungs, and muscles of respiration, obtains from the air the oxygen necessary for cellular metabolism; it also returns to the air the carbon dioxide that forms as a waste product of such metabolism. Humans need oxygen to provide their energy, and the respiratory system does this. ⁶⁰ (Robert A. Klocke, Neil S. Cherniack, Ewald R. |Encyclopedia Britannica; 2023)

(4) The circulatory system, composed of the heart, blood, and blood vessels, circulates a transport fluid throughout the body, providing the cells with a steady supply of oxygen and nutrients and carrying away waste products such as carbon dioxide and toxic nitrogen compounds. ⁶¹ (Michael Francis Oliver, Bernard Edward Matthews, M. Elizabeth Rogers |Encyclopedia; 2023)

A: The blood circulation system helps to energize or provide energy to transport, deliver and move energy and nutrients to different cells and tissues of the human body. B: Also, the circulatory system collects harmful substances from the organs of the body and sends them to the kidneys or lungs for elimination in order to provide security of the human body.

https://www.freepik.com/free-vector/human-internal-organs-infographic-poster_6168813.htm

(5) The human digestive system, system used in the human body for the process of digestion. The human digestive system consists primarily of the digestive tract, or the series of structures and organs through which food and liquids pass during their processing into forms absorbable into the bloodstream. The system also consists of the structures through which wastes pass in the process of elimination and other organs that contribute juices necessary for the digestive process. composed of the mouth, esophagus, stomach, and intestines, breaks down food into usable substances (nutrients and energy), which are then absorbed from the blood or lymph. ⁶² (Nicholas Carr Hightower, William Sircus, Harvey J. Dworken Encyclopaedia Britannica, 2023) A: The digestive system has been selected by natural selection based on the supply of energy and nutrients. For example, teeth evolved to break food so that food is digested more easily and help provide energy and nutrients to the body. The tongue is responsible for tasting the food that humans need to provide energy and nutrients. Vitamins and proteins are delicious. Because the body needs them to supply its energy and nutrients. B: But the taste of spoiled food is unpleasant to tongue because it reminds the body of safety (provide security). This selection has evolved to ensure the safety or for provide security of body tissues and cells. this system also eliminates the unusable or excess portion of the food as fecal matter for provide security. (6) excretion, the process by which animals rid themselves of waste products and of the nitrogenous by-products of metabolism. Through excretion organisms control osmotic pressure—the balance between inorganic ions and water—and maintain acid-base balance. The process thus promotes homeostasis, the constancy of the organism's internal environment. Every organism, from the smallest protist to the largest mammal, must rid itself of the potentially

harmful by-products of its own vital activities. This process in living things is called elimination, which may be considered to encompass all of the various mechanisms and processes by which life forms dispose of or throw off waste products, toxic substances, and dead portions of the organism. The nature of the process and of the specialized structures developed for waste disposal vary greatly with the size and complexity of the organism. Kidneys have evolved in multicellular animals as a highly sophisticated channel for waste disposal, and they function to regulate the levels of water, salts, and organic materials in the bodies of higher animals. Materials eliminated via the kidney include nitrogenous waste products (ammonia, uric acid, urea, creatine, creatinine, and amino acids), excess quantities of salts and water that may be taken into the body, and various other organic materials produced by life-sustaining chemical reactions. Functionally, the kidney is a microfilter that initially removes dissolved as well as some suspended materials from the circulatory system, along with large quantities of water. These substances are differentially reabsorbed into the blood by various kidney structures during urine formation to a degree that varies considerably throughout the animal kingdom. For example, animals that absorb large quantities of water into their bodies (such as freshwater fishes) excrete copious quantities of water in their urine. The reverse is true of many desert animals, who must conserve water and therefore produce a thick, semisolid urine. The kidney, in its various stages of evolution, functions at the expense of considerable metabolic energy and cannot be considered to be a passive system. ⁶³(Fenton Crosland Kelley, James Arthur Ramsay 2023 Britannica) The excretory system, composed of the kidneys, ureters, urinary bladder, and urethra, removes toxic nitrogen compounds and other wastes from the blood for provide security human body.

(7) The nervous system, organized group of cells specialized for the conduction of electrochemical stimuli from sensory receptors through a network to the site at which a response occurs. All living organisms are able to detect changes within themselves and in their environments. Changes in the external environment include those of light, temperature, sound, motion, and odour, while changes in the internal environment include those in the position of the head and limbs as well as in the internal organs. Once detected, these internal and external changes must be analyzed and acted upon in order to survive. As life on Earth evolved and the environment became more complex, the survival of organisms depended upon how well they could respond to changes in their surroundings. One factor necessary for survival was a speedy reaction or response. Since communication from one cell to another by chemical means was too slow to be adequate for survival, a system evolved that allowed for faster reaction. That system was the nervous system, which is based upon the almost instantaneous transmission of electrical impulses from one region of the body to another along specialized nerve cells called neurons. The simplest type of response is a direct one-to-one stimulus-response reaction. A change in the environment is the stimulus; the reaction of the organism to it is the response. Nervous systems are of two general types, diffuse and centralized. In the diffuse type of system, found in lower invertebrates, there is no brain, and neurons are distributed throughout the organism in a netlike pattern. In the centralized systems of higher invertebrates and vertebrates, a portion of the nervous system has a dominant role in coordinating information and directing responses. This centralization reaches its culmination in vertebrates, which have a well-developed brain and spinal cord. Impulses are carried to and from the brain and spinal cord by nerve fibres that make up the peripheral nervous system. ⁶⁴(Solomon D. Erulkar Thomas L. Lentz 2023 Britannica) nervous system, composed of the sensory organs, brain, spinal cord, and nerves, transmits, integrates, and analyzes sensory information and carries impulses to effect the appropriate muscular or glandular responses for provide energy and for provide security and for reproduction and adaptation to environmental. (8) The endocrine system, composed of the hormone-secreting glands and tissues, provides a chemical communications network for coordinating various body processes for provide energy and for provide security and for reproduction and adaptation to environmental. (9) The reproductive system, composed of the male or female sex organs, enables reproduction and thereby ensures the continuation of the species, transfer genes. 10- Vision and hearing both evolved in order to provide energy and nutrients, provide security,

adapt to environmental conditions and transfer genes to the next generation in animals and humans. Hearing and vision help humans to identify dangers and enemies and provide itself security. Like hearing the voice of a lion and a leopard, the voice of human enemies can alert a person and help ensure his safety. Hearing and sight help humans to find a game and tree fruit, to provide energy and nutrients. For example, hearing the sound of the river and water, hearing the sound of animals, seeing the fruits and seeds of plants. Also, hearing and vision help humans adapt to environmental conditions such as temperature and humidity, etc. Humans can find a mate for reproduction with the help of hearing and vision.

Different types of cells in the human body, in fact, some of them directly and some indirectly function to provide energy, provide security, reproduce and adapt to environmental conditions. In other words, if we pay close attention, the different cells of the body that make up the different tissues of the body, all by natural selection based on the fundamental principles of the new hypothesis, i.e. 1- supply of energy and nutrients (all the substances that the body needs) 2- Provide security 3-Compatibility with environmental conditions 4-Transferring genes to the next generation, were choice and selected.

Interpretation of the cause of the evolution of the Covid-19 virus based on the fundamental principles of the new hypothesis.

The Covid-19 virus, which first appeared in Wuhan, China in 2019, multiplied so quickly that the human immune system could not destroy it. The only way was to quarantine the infected so that they do not come into contact with healthy people. The virus mutated into alpha, delta, and micron, etc. Successful mutations were selected based on the fundamental principles of natural selection. The energy supply, security and reproduction of the virus may be weakened or strengthened by mutation.

The alpha virus spread rapidly because the human immune system was weak against the alpha virus. In other words, man could not provide his security, against the alpha virus. Therefore, the alpha virus multiplied in the human body. Here, human security is selected in competition with virus security by natural selection. The virus continued to survive and reproduce by killing many people in the world. Because the alpha virus could protect itself against the human immune system. Also, the virus used the human body to supply its energy and nutrients. Therefore, the virus was successful in providing energy and nutrients and was successful in providing its own security and survived and multiplied. Until viruses are destroyed by the human immune system, they exploit the human body as a source of energy and nutrients.

But the discovery of corona vaccine and its injection strengthened the human immune system. Therefore, the virus could not protect itself against the human immune system. This time it was humans who won the competition for provide security. So humans survived and the alpha virus was almost extinct.

But the virus mutated again and Delta virus appeared. The delta virus could survive longer against the human immune system than the alpha virus. This made the human immune system unable to destroy him. He killed many people to provide himself with energy and nutrients. Delta virus multiplied and spread by providing energy and nutrients and securing itself. But by injecting the second dose of the vaccine, the human body became stronger or could better protect itself against the delta virus (provide security). Delta virus was destroyed by the human immune system and could not get its energy and nutrients from humans. His reproduction stopped.

Again, the corona virus mutated and caused changes in provide security or securing the safety of the COVID-19 virus against the human immune system. The mutant Omicron virus came and killed many people around the world. Because it was able to protect itself against the human immune system. Omicron could provide its security against the human immune system with a higher quality than the previous species. This caused him to take the energy and nutrients he needed from humans. The

Omicron virus had a stronger immune system, faster reproduction and energy supply, and used the vital organs of the human body, such as the lungs, for provide food and energy.

But injecting the second and third doses of the vaccine strengthened the human body's immunity and, along with the quarantine, kept the human body away from the virus. Based on this, humans can better protect themselves, the new virus was destroyed by the strong immune system of the human body. Humans improve their security by producing vaccines and provide their security against viruses.

Interpretation of sickle cell disease selection based on the fundamental principles of the new hypothesis by natural selection in malaria patients

Background The gene for sickle hemoglobin (HbS) is a prime example of natural selection. It is generally believed that its current prevalence in many tropical populations reflects selection for the carrier form (sickle cell trait [HbAS]) through a survival advantage against death from malaria. 65(Thomas N Williams, Tabitha W Mwangi, Sammy Wambua, Neal D Alexander, Moses Kortok, Robert W Snow, Kevin Marsh2005) In the area of malaria prevalence, sickle hemoglobin gene confers immunity to its heterozygous carrier. (secures its carrier, Or provides the security of its carrier.)

Sickle cell anemia is one of a group of inherited disorders known as sickle cell disease. It affects the shape of the red blood cells that carry oxygen to all parts of the body. 66(Xuejin Li a, Ming Dao b, George Lykotrafitis c d, George Em Karniadakis 2017)

interpretation; A heterozygous carrier can provide security against malaria. But the homozygous carrier cannot deliver enough oxygen to the body tissue, and cannot provide the energy and nutrients the body needs.

Interpretation of the evolution of tetrapods or the purpose of foot evolution based on the fundamental principles of the new hypothesis

Walking tetrapods and finding food/Several extant fishes have a number of morphological and behavioural traits that facilitate moving out of water to escape predation, find food or new habitats, or lay eggs. The most simplistic and least anatomically derived method to move across a dry horizontal surface is to undulate or flip the body by modifying the same motor programs that facilitate swimming and escape responses in water, as is seen in eels, killifishes and sticklebacks. 67(Brooke E. Flammang, Apinun Suvarnaraksha, ...Daphne Soares 2016)

Interpretation of the evolution of tetrapods or the evolution of the foot based on the fundamental principles of the new hypothesis: 1- Escape from being hunted means that the evolution of the foot is useful for ensuring one's own safety. 2- The purpose of finding food is the evolution of the foot to provide energy and nutrients. 3-Finding habitat for egg laying means evolution of walking or evolution of legs for reproduction and transfer of genes to the next generation.

Interpretation of the evolution of different wings and legs in vertebrates based on the fundamental principles of the new hypothesis. Vertebrate limb diversity was produced by changes in the number, position and shape of structures that can be traced to Ordovician (463–439 Myr) through Late Devonian (409–362 Myr) fossils. The demands of feeding and locomotion in Ordovician and Silurian seas led to a surprising variability of the earliest known appendages: some forms possessed a continuous anterior fin that ran the length of the body, others had paired fins that projected immediately behind a head shield, and still other primitive vertebrates had no paired fins at all. Some regions of vertebrate appendages are more variable than others. The invention of flippers, wings and other specialized limbs often involved significant changes in the pattern of distal structures rather than proximal ones. 68(Shubin, N., Tabin, C. & Carroll, S. Fossils, 1997)

Interpretation of the evolution of different wings and legs in vertebrates based on the fundamental principles of the new hypothesis; The evolution of all types of legs in amphibians, reptiles and mammals and the evolution of wings in birds and bats has been to meet basic needs. The basic needs are providing energy and nutrients and providing security, adapting to environmental conditions, and transferring genes to the next generation. Evolution took place in the morphology and ecology and characteristics of alleles, which were formed under the influence of the fundamental principles of the new hypothesis. or were formed under the influence of basic needs.

Summary and conclusion

What is chosen? Why is it chosen? Scientists say; Natural selection acts non-randomly, what does that mean? By theoretical research and finding a new hypothesis, I found out what is selected and for what. Natural selection operates non-randomly, i.e. natural selection is most likely based on the basic principles of energy and nutrient supply, provide security, adaptation to environmental conditions such as temperature, humidity, pressure, wind, etc., and reproductive success and transferring genes to the next generation, makes selection and choice. Maybe this new hypothesis with a new attitude to the theory of evolution and biology will transform it.

Looking back, we find that those that were destroyed and disappeared, whether genes, individuals, populations, or taxa such as dinosaurs, all of them either could not provide their energy and nutrients in front of competitors, or could not secure themselves. Or they could not adapt to the environmental conditions such as temperature, pressure, humidity, etc., or the competitors adapted better to the environmental conditions, or the competitors were more successful in providing their energy and nutrients, or the competitors had traits which were more successful in reproduction and transfer of genes.

In the definition of evolution and adaptation and natural selection based on the fundamental principles of the new hypothesis, there is no intelligent, pre-planned and ultimate goal. For example, a giraffe's neck is not programmed or evolved to feed on leaves. Evolution does not know in advance what

organism it is going to produce. But evolution must work according to principles. I mean of purposefulness in the adaptation of different organisms in species, populations, and individuals, 1-adaptation to provide energy and nutrients, 2-adaptation to provide security, 3-adaptation to environmental conditions such as temperature, humidity, pressure, wind , etc., and 4-adaptation for transfer genes to the next generation.

Statements and Declarations

The author confirms that he has not received any financial or non-financial resources related to this article.

The author has no competing interests to declare related to the content of this article.

Hello, dear professor

I apologize for taking up your time.

I wrote an article about a new hypothesis that reveals the fundamental principles of natural selection. What is selected by natural selection? Why is it chosen? In this paper I argue that I have found the principles that are selected by natural selection.

The important thing is that this article is a preprint. Maybe there is a problem with the translation. Maybe the wording and arrangement of the content is not correct. I want you to pay attention to the general topic of the article, the new hypothesis.

I am waiting for your feedback. Please send me your comments, suggestions and criticisms.

Muhammad.yousef.arbab@gmail.com

The new hypothesis is not about selection at the molecular level. In this article, I will not discuss structural selection, selection based on the components of molecules and cells, selection based on biochemical laws and physics and chemistry, and other selections. In this article, I would like to discuss another type of selection at the population, individual, allele, and cell levels.

tip; There may be other principles that are selected by natural selection. But in this article, I will examine the fundamental principles of the new hypothesis, namely, providing energy and nutrients and providing security.

Point 2; I have other articles to publish that present new psychological hypotheses based on the fundamental principles of the new hypothesis. In other articles, I have discussed the reason for the evolution of music, the evolution of human societies, the evolution of cultures and values, the evolution of inventions, sociological theory, economic theories, the cause of human pain and suffering, the cause of happiness and satisfaction, the cause of the behavior of creatures, the compatibility of populations, I explain the evolution of populations based on the fundamental principles of the new hypothesis.

Is it possible that the new hypothesis provides a new understanding and interpretation of evolution and biology?

Dear readers, if you find new and useful concepts in this article, please send the article link to science enthusiasts, scientists, professors and students.

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